

21GRD07 PlasticTrace

Deliverable 3: Report on the harmonised Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) of the developed SMPs (10 μm - 100 μm) characterisation methods in terms of: (i) chemical identity of the SMPs polymer type; (ii) physical particle characterisation and quantification, size distribution and particle morphologies; and (iii) quantification of the mass fraction in complex matrices.

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:
Umweltbundesamt (UBA)

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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1 Executive Summary

This document outlines the development and harmonization of procedures for the characterization of Small Microplastic Particles (SMP) in complex food and environmental matrices. Initially, existing documentation, including publications and proprietary protocols from the partners, was collected and distributed.

Two matrices were investigated in detail: one food-related matrices and one environmental matrix. These included infant milk powder and suspended particulate matter (SPM). Infant milk powder was purchased from each partner, while the suspended particulate matter (SPM) was collected and characterized. The characterization of these matrices involved analysing elemental composition, organic carbon content, and the background level of SMP.

Specifically, the SMP containing tablets produced in WP1 were selected as a reference material and spiked into the matrices. Tablets with different amount of SMP of PET and PP from were used, as well as tablets with different particle numbers. Different spiking levels were considered, using different SMP batches and different content of matrices. The analyses were performed using various techniques, including thermo-analytical methods such as Thermal Extraction Desorption Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (TED-GC/MS) and Pyrolysis Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (Py-GC/MS), as well as spectroscopic methods like Micro Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (μ -FTIR), μ -Raman, and Quantum Cascade Laser Laser Direct Infrared (QCL-LDIR).

A series of standard operating procedures (SOPs) were compiled, employing different technical approaches to identify and characterize SMP in these complex matrices. These include sample preparation protocols for oxidative and enzymatic treatment to reduce the organic matrix, as well as density separations steps, using different salt solutions to reduce inorganic components. The changes of spiked SMP mass fraction and particle numbers in size distribution and recovery rates including error derivations were determined.

In sum two finalized SOPs for the spiking of milk with PET were provided. This matrix only needs a reduction of organic matrix. Acceptable recovery rates of more than 80 % with error derivations of around 10 - 20 % were determined for mass determination and particle number-based methods.

For SPM with PET or PP only indicative information could be implemented in the SOP. This matrix needs a reduction of organic and inorganic matrix and is therefore more complex. However, recovery rates of more around 120 % with error derivations of around 10 - 20 % were determined for mass determination. For detection methods of particle number-based methods only good recovery rates were determined for very high spiking levels. For moderate and realistic spiking levels only recovery rates of less than 50 % could be developed. Here the number of repetitions is still very low.

During the development of all SOPs, it became very clear that protocols developed with thermo-analytical SMP detection are faster to realise than with spectroscopic methods. However, with thermo-analytical methods only relatively high levels can be reliably analysed here compared to the matrix. The application of spectroscopic methods is therefore than preferred, when low SMP contamination are expected in a matrix.

The different SOPs developed for the various techniques and matrices will be soon available on Zenodo at the PlasticTrace Community page (<https://zenodo.org/communities/plastictrace/>).

2 Introduction

This report presents the development and optimization of sample preparation methods for the detection of small microplastics (SMP) in complex matrices. The matrices investigated include food-related samples, as well as environmentally relevant samples. For these samples defined amounts of particles masses or particle numbers were selected and spiked. Their quantities are related to concentration, which are observed in reality.

The preparation and characterisation of SMP reference materials, produced by BAM as part of Work Package 1 (WP1), is excluded from this document, please, refer to Deliverable 1.1 of Plastic Trace, as well as various publications submitted recently; namely:

- PlasticTrace - Deliverable 1.1: Summary report on the development of pristine SI traceable reference materials for SMPs (10 μm - 100 μm), representative of partially degraded/naturally aged samples in complex food and environmental matrices, and for realistic polydisperse size distributions and irregular shapes
- Quality-by-design and current good practices for the production of test and reference materials for micro- and nano-plastic research

Korinna Altmann, Lukas Wimmer, Victor Alcolea-Rodriguez, Tassilo Waniek, Volker Wachtendorf, Kay Matzdorf, Dmitri Ciornii, Petra Fengler, Frank Milczewski, Itziar Otazo-Aseguinolaza, Manuel Ferrer, Miguel A. Bañares, Raquel Portela, Lea Ann Dailey

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- Lactose Tablets as suitable Microplastics Reference Material to support validation studies and quality control

Korinna Altmann, Yosri Wiesner, Petra Fengler, Christiane Weimann, Claudia Drago, Ulrike Braun, Marta Fadda, Mara Putzu, Soledad Muniategui Lorenzo, Carmen Moscoso-Pérez, Verónica Fernández-González, Paul-Tiberiu Miclea, Nizar Benismail, Laureen Coic, Alina Maltseva, Bert van Bavel, Vilde Kloster Snekkevik, Andy M. Booth, Lisbeth Sorensen, Enrica Alasonati, Carine Chivas-Joly, Andrea Maria Giovannozzi

Submitted to Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances, 18.09.2025

- Optimization of tablet processing as a reference material for microplastic detection methods

Mara Putzu, Yosri Wiesner, Christiane Weimann, Vasile Dan Hodoroba, Soledad Muniategui Lorenzo, Verónica Fernández-González, Andy M. Booth, Amaia Igartua, Nizar Benismail, Laureen Coic, Carine Chivas-Joly, Ivana Fenoglio, Andrea Mario Rossi, Andrea Mario Giovannozzi, Korinna Altmann

Submitted to Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry ABC-01167-2025, 11.08.2025

The outcome of the task “Data Treatment and Harmonization” is demonstrated in a separate publication:

- Inter-instrument definition of valid criteria for the automatic identification of microplastics by micro-Raman spectroscopy

Ricardo Jorge Neves Bettencourt da Silva, Rafaela Fernandes; Paul-Tiberiu Miclea; Marta Fadda; Mara Putzu; Alessio Sacco; Andrea M. Rossi; Andrea M. Giovannozzi; Marta Barbaresi; Matteo Masino; Monica Mattarozzi; Maria Careri; Carla Palma; José Almeida; Claudia Drago; Olivier Pellegrino; Raquel Quendera; Ulrike Braun

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The present deliverable gives also an overview about used methods and material, as well as results. This includes also an initial characterization of each matrix, to estimate various key compositional parameters, such as organic and inorganic content, total carbon content, elemental composition and microplastic background contamination.

Because the sample preparation is strongly connected to the subsequent analysis technique, the deliverable is structured in various protocols for the different matrices and the applied analysis techniques.

The sample preparation protocols include methods for reduction of organic content (using hydrogen peroxide, enzymatic treatment) as well as reduction of inorganic content by density separation (using CaCl₂, and NaI).

The detection systems considered in PlasticTrace for this task include analytical methodologies intended for determining particle numbers, in particular, vibrational spectroscopy, such as μ -Raman and μ -Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (μ -FTIR), as well as quantum-cascade laser-based spectroscopy (QCL-LDIR) and mass fractions, in particular, thermo-analytical methods, such as thermal extraction desorption gas chromatography mass spectrometry (TED-GC/MS) and Pyrolysis gas chromatography mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS).

The matrices investigated include food-related samples such as drinking water and infant milk powder, as well as environmentally relevant samples such as suspended particulate matter (SPM) and sewage sludge. For drinking water no additional sample preparation was needed, therefore no data are shown in this deliverable. For the other matrices Table 1 gives an overview about the planned and achieved results.

According to the project proposal different spiking levels for the different samples were planned and realised. A few derivations were done, because of the complexity of sample preparation. However, for SPM an additional very low SMP contamination was considered, because the planned value was higher, than observed.

*Table: 1 Overview about the realised investigated materials in WP2.
The target values are "assumption" and are the basis for spiking calculation related to real scenarios.*

Milk Powder (ca. 100 g/l)	Suspended particular matter (SPM) (ca. 50 mg/l)
Target value: < 1.000 n/l Target value: < 1 μ g/l	Target value: > 1.000 n/l Target value: > 1 μ g/l
Target value: 10 n/g Target value: 0,01 μ g/g	Target value: 20.000 n/g Target value: 20 μ g/g
Mainly organic matrix	Mainly inorganic matrix
Oxidative digestion	Oxidative digestion / density separation

The results of all applied techniques are related to the overall sample composition and recovery rates are provided.

3 Objectives

The objective of this work was to develop an efficient and accurate sample preparation method and to reach a consensus on the preparation of food and environmental matrices as drinking water, milk powder, suspended particulate matter and sewage sludge for the detection of small microplastic particles (SMPs) ranging from 10-100 μm .

These methods include – depended on the used matrix - (i) enrichment prior to analysis, (ii) selective removal of natural background organic/inorganic matter, (iii) size fractionation/isolation, and (iv) homogenisation and partition steps. The sample preparation methods demonstrate a negligible effect on the particle characteristics and polymer compositions of samples. The developed sample preparation protocols are applicable for detection methods which includes (i) characterisation of chemical identity of the SMPs/NPs polymer type; (ii) physical particle characterisation and quantification, size distribution and particle morphologies; and (iii) quantification of the mass fraction in complex matrices.

To demonstrate the validity and applicability of the methods inter-laboratory comparison within the consortium was realised. As part of the comparison, best practice guidance on the traceable measurement and characterisation of SMPs in food and environmental matrices were developed.

The measurement infrastructure developed in in the project by the measurement supply chain, supported the development of standards in different technical committees, such as ISO TC 147, ISO TC 61 and CEN TC 444, in which partners PlasticTrace active cooperates. Important findings were made for the implementation of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (2024/3019) and the Drinking Water Directive (2020/2184).

4 Methodologies

4.1 Characterization of matrices

Particle size distribution (HEREON)

The grain size distribution of SPM was determined by laser diffraction (Analysette 22 NanoTec, Fritsch, Idar-Oberstein, Germany). Results are expressed as the fraction of the sample smaller than the corresponding particle diameter. Mean values and standard deviations (SD) are calculated with $n \leq 3$.

Composition of matrix (HEREON, UBA)

Through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), the sample was heated at rate of 10 K min^{-1} , up to $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under inert atmosphere (N_2) and up to $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under synthetic air. The mass loss was measured, and the decomposition temperature of the compounds could be determined. In this study, the percentage of pyrolysis product was calculated and the peak area, given by differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTG) curve, was assessed for a qualitative investigation of the sample preparation.

Total organic content (TOC), determination of total organic carbon, was made following method (DIN EN 15936) to quantify elemental carbon. Samples were weighed onto a silver foil boat and wetted with 10% hydrochloric acid. The weights were measured as triplicate determinations. Subsequently, the silver boats were dried at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a drying oven and packed tightly with pressing tools. The packed silver boats were additionally wrapped in tin foil (modifier) and entered the $950 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ combustion tube via a sample introduction system. The atmosphere in the combustion tube consisted of synthetic air. The carrier gas flow (200 ml/min , pressure 1-1.1 bar) carried the gaseous combustion products. The resulting CO_2 is quantitatively detected by an NDIR detector. The NDIR was calibrated using a soil reference material (0.651% TOC, calibration range 0.00058-0.0916% TOC) and potassium hydrogen phthalate (47.05% TOC, calibration range 0.048-0.379% TOC). Deviations of the method up to $\pm 10 \%$ are tolerable. For analysis of organic content by loss-on-ignition, aliquots of approximately 0.5 g were taken from the original sample and were placed in cleaned and dried crucibles in the oven at $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 8 h. The average of 3 aliquots was determined.

Composition of the inorganic components (HEREON, UBA)

For the analysis of the inorganic composition of the SPM material samples using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) were digested in triplicates of $100 \text{ mg} \pm 5 \text{ mg}$ SPM using 5 mL HNO_3 , 2 mL HCl and 1 mL HBF_4 . Based on a microwave assisted acid digestion using a MARS Xpress microwave (CEM Corp., Kamp Lintfort, Germany) in 55 mL pre-cleaned TFM digestion vessels following the protocol of Zimmermann et al. (2020) (<https://doi.org/10.1039/D0AY01049A>). TFM digestion vessels were pre-cleaned using an ETC EVO II (ANALAB, Hoenheim, France) acid vapor cleaner with HNO_3 (65% w/w) and type I reagent grade water. Digested samples were quantitatively transferred to 50 mL graduated, PP vessels (DigiTUBE®; SCP Science, Quebec, Canada) precleaned with HNO_3 (2% w/w) and filled to a total volume of 50 mL with type I reagent grade water. The marine sediment reference material GBW-07311 and the plankton reference material BCR-414 were treated similarly and digested for validation purposes. The reference materials were quantitatively digested by the presented digestion method resulting in clear, particle free digests. Sample digests were measured using an ICP-MS/MS (Agilent 8800, Agilent Technologies, Santa Barbara CA, USA) coupled to a prepFAST M5 system (Elemental Scientific, Omaha, Nebraska, USA) H_2 and N_2O were employed as reaction gases in MS/MS mode for the quantified elements. Quantified mass-to-charge ratios and corresponding cell modes were selected based on achieved sensitivity, as well as by non-occurrence of isobaric and polyatomic interferences. The instrument was tuned daily to obtain optimal measuring conditions using a tune solution containing Li, Co, Y, Ce and Tl ($10 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). External calibration covering a concentration range from $0 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ to $10,000 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Mg, Al, K, Ca, Ti, Fe, Mn, Ba and P and $0 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ to $100 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for the remaining elements, automatically diluted by the prepFAST M5 system from two stock solutions, as well as online dosed internal standards ($10 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Rh and Ir) were used for quantification. Wash blanks were measured after each sample triplicate to monitor and avoid potential carry-over effects. Limits of detection (LOD) and limits of quantification (LOQ) were calculated from procedural blanks, including three times the standard deviation ($3 \times \text{SD}$) for LOD and ten times ($10 \times \text{SD}$) for LOQ. Outliers were determined according to Dean and Dixon ($P = 0.95$) and were not included in further evaluation of the data.

For the elemental analysis using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) of milk powder samples were first digested with nitric acid prior to measurement. Digestion was carried out in accordance with DIN EN ISO 15587-2:2002-07) for digestion in a closed system and a MarsXpress laboratory microwave from CEM with Xpress digestion vessels). The subsequent measurement of the digestion solutions was carried out in accordance with DIN EN ISO 11885:2009-09 using an ICP-OES measuring device, model Optima 8300 from Perkin Elmer. The elements Ca, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, and Zn were determined. An ICP multi-element standard solution from Merck (multi-element standard solution elements in concentrated nitric acid) was used as the stock solution for calibrating the elements. Seven reference solutions in the range between 5 µg/l and 1500 µg/l were prepared from this stock solution. As part of quality assurance, a so-called method blank value was measured. In addition, an independent control standard was measured. The evaluation was performed using Syngistix software, version 5.1.0.0293 from Perkin Elmer, by adjusting the baselines (sub-point correction) and adjusting the calibration points.

Microplastic background contamination (HEREON, IHi, UDC)

Using QCL-LDIR for microplastic background contamination in SPM a sample weight of around 5 g was used and pretreated using H₂O₂ (30 %) at 40 °C for 12 h. After filtering the remaining solids, using PTFE filters (D=47 mm, 5 µm), a density separation was performed with ZnCl₂ followed by a final filtration using PTFE filters. For the QCL-LDIR measurements the filter cake was transferred to MirrIR low-e microscope slides (7.5 x 2.5 cm, Kevley Technologies).

Light microscopy was used to analyse the background contamination of SPM. The sample preparation was done using sample weight of around 10 mg, with a previous digestion treatment with H₂O₂ (10 %) for 72 h. After sieving through 50 µm metal sieve, a density separation was performed with NaI ($\rho \sim 1.8 \text{ g/cm}^3$) during 24 h. The final filtration was done with a glass fiber filter (47 mm, 1.2 µm pore). Subsequent analysis using attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was done.

In addition, the SPM was analyzed to determine its SMP background content by Py-GC-MS. Details of the method can be found below in section 4.3. Mean values and standard deviation (SD) are calculated with n=10.

4.2 Materials

All chemicals were of analytical quality grade.

For the preparation of pre-treated samples various filtration setups, including filter materials were available. An overview of used filters is given in Table 2. For filtration a dedicated SOP is available, as derived from the PlasticTrace project itself:

- SOP “Filtration of Nano- and Microplastic Particles from liquid solution are provided by plastic trace” (<https://zenodo.org/records/14850536>)

Table 2: Overview on the filter materials used in the PlasticTrace project

Filter type	Mesh size / porosity / µm	Diameter / mm	Application	(SMP) Analytical detection
glass fiber filter	2,7	50	Pre-running experiments	TGA (UBA)
metal filter	5-6	50	Pre-running experiments	TGA (UBA)
crucible filter	5-6	9	SMP determination	TED-GC/MS (BAM)
silicon filter	5, 10	9	SMP determination	Raman, µ-FTIR (INRIM)
Alumina (anodisc)	0.2	25	SMP determination	µ FTIR (Syke).
Polyester gold coated filter	0.8	25	SMP determination	QCL-LDIR (UDC)
Glass microfiber	0.7	55	Pretreatment	Py-GC/MS (UDC)
Glass microfiber	1.6	13	SMP determination	Py-GC/MS (UDC)
PTFE	5	47	SMP determination	QCL-LDIR (HERION)
Polycarbonate membrane	5	9	SMP determination	µ-FTIR (IHi)

4.3 Mass-based detection techniques for SMP Determination

TED-GC/MS (BAM)

Crucibles filter for TED-GC/MS measurements have a high of 13 mm with 9 mm in diameter (GKD - Gebr. Kufferath AG, Düren, Germany). The TED-GC/MS is a multi-step analysis procedure, in which first the organic compounds of a sample are pyrolyzed in a TGA2 thermobalance (MettlerToledo) under a nitrogen flow of 30 mL/min from 200-500 °C at a heating rate of 10 K/min. The decomposition products were collected on a solid phase (40 °C, SorbStar, Envea, Vohenstrauß, DE) via a heated coupling module (240 °C, Gerstel, Mülheim a.d.R., DE and BAM). The loaded solid phase was transported to the TDU-GC/MS by an autosampler (MPS2, Gerstel). The desorption of the decomposition products took place in the thermal desorption module (TDU, 50-200 °C, 5 min isothermal, He current, Gerstel), the cryofocussing in the cold feed system (KAS, -100 °C, Gerstel). Injection was carried out from there by rapid heating (-100-270 °C, 12 K/s) onto the separation column (HP5ms, 1 ml/min He, 40-300 °C, 5 K/min, Agilent, Palo Alto, USA) in the GC system (7890, Agilent). After chromatographic separation, detection was performed in a mass spectrometer (EI, 70 eV, scan-mode, Agilent). Identification and quantification were done using the specific pyrolysis products. For PET Acetophenone (105 m/z), Vinylbenzoate (105 m/z), Ethylbenzoate (105, 150 m/z), Benzoic acid (150 m/z), Biphenyl (154 m/z), Divinyl terephthalate (175 m/z) and Terephthalic acid ethyl vinyl ester (105 m/z) was used for quantification, whereas for PP 2,4,6,8-Tetramethylundec-10-ene (111 m/z), 2,4,6,8-Tetramethylundec-10-ene (111 m/z) and 2,4,6,8-Tetramethylundec-10-ene (111 m/z) was used.

The quantification was carried out using matrix dependent calibration. The calibration curves for all specific pyrolysis products were based on six points. For this purpose, six samples of milk powder were prepared using citric acid at 50 °C. The respective filter residue was spiked with a defined mass of PET (0 mg, 12 mg, 16 mg, 28 mg, 40 mg, 61 mg). The calibration curves for all specific pyrolysis products were generated using six points. For this purpose, the linear function is being rearranged to determine the spiked PET mass. PP was identified and quantified in SPM by using the PP specific markers. Similar to the PET, matrix dependent calibration was done with 0, 1,4, 10 and 15 µg of PP.

The limit of detection and limit of quantification were determined using the signal-to-noise ratio.

Py-GC/MS (UDC)

After the sample preparation of the different matrices the residue was analyzed by Py-GC/MS. In a first step, the samples are heated up in an inert atmosphere until decomposition (pyrolysis). In a second step, the resulting decomposition products are directly separated on a GC column.

For the direct analysis by Py-GC/MS of the filter with the PET particles, the dissolution is filtered using a stainless steel filter holder with a Whatman glass fibre filter (13 mm filter size, 1.6 µm pore size) and a 20 mL glass syringe connected to a Visiprep™ vacuum manifold (Supelco Sigma-Aldrich Co). The filter was folded and inserted into the pyrolysis ECO-cup (80 µL, Frontier Labs) and dried in an oven at 40°C for a minimum of 4 hours, then samples were placed directly into the pyrolyzer.

Analyses were performed using a Frontier Multi-Shot Pyrolyzer (PY-3030D) (Frontier Labs, Japan) coupled with an Agilent 8860 GC and an Agilent 5977A MSD (Py-GC/MS) (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The pyrolyzer operated in single-shot mode with pyrolysis at 600 °C for 0.5 min. The pyrolyzer interface and GC inlet temperatures were set to 300 °C, and the split ratio was 100:1. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1 mL/min. Separation was achieved using a HP-5MS UI capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 µm film thickness, and 0.25 mm internal diameter). The column oven temperature was programmed to start at 40 °C for 2 min, then increased at a rate of 20°C/min up to 325°C (14 min), followed by an increase of 30 °C up to 340 °C. The transfer line temperature was maintained at 320 °C, the ion source temperature at 280 °C, and the quadrupole temperature at 150 °C. The ion source operated in Full Scan mode. PET was quantified using Benzoic acid as marker (m/z 77;105;122) and Biphenyl (m/z 154), Benzene (m/z 78) and Vinyl benzoate (m/z 51;77;105) as confirmation markers, using external calibration. For samples requiring derivatization, TMAH (tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide 25 % in MeOH) was used, and the marker for PET quantification was dimethyl terephthalate (m/z 163, 194, 135).

4.4 Particle detection techniques for SMP Determination

μ-FTIR (Syke)

For FTIR, an imaging system (Bruker Lumos II FPA) was used in transmission mode. The entire effective area of the filter was analysed with the settings as follows: spectral range 3600 to 1250 cm^{-1} , spectral resolution 8 cm^{-1} , and one scan with binning 2x2. The background (10 scans) was measured from the clean area of the sample filter. An analysis took 4.5 h and produced 29 Gb of raw data files.

μ-FTIR (INRIM)

FTIR analysis was carried out using a Thermo Scientific™ Nicolet iN10 infrared microscope, equipped with a KBr/Ge beam splitter and a mercury cadmium telluride (MCT) detector. The filtration area was imaged with a 15x objective (numerical aperture: 0.7; working distance: 16 mm). Spectra were acquired in the 650 - 4000 cm^{-1} range, an acquisition time of 3 s and 16 scans per spectrum at a 8 cm^{-1} Resolution. Data acquisition and particle identification was conducted using Omnic Picta software (v9.16). Particles were considered correctly identified when the Hit Quality Index (HQI) > 80 %, while spectra with 50 % < HQI < 80 % were manually evaluated for identification. Identical conditions were employed for both PET tablet RM and fortified milk samples.

μ-RAMAN (INRIM)

Analysis was performed on milk samples using a LabRAM Odyssey Raman spectrometer (HORIBA Scientific, France SAS) equipped with a CCD detector. Initially the entire filter was imaged using a 10x objective (OLYMPUS, numerical aperture: 0.25) under darkfield illumination system to acquire a panoramic mosaic of the filter. All subsequent measurements were carried out with a 50x long working distance objective (OLYMPUS, numerical aperture = 0.5), also in darkfield mode in order to minimize the contribution of the filter pores and facilitate image analysis. Three regions were randomly selected across the entire filter, each measuring 2.5 mm x 1.5 mm (3.8 mm^2), collectively representing approximately 55 % of the total filtering area. The data obtained were scaled to estimate PET particle number across the full filtration surface.

Spectra were acquired in the range of 620-1760 cm^{-1} using a 633 nm, an excitation laser with a power of 12 mW, an exposure time of 1 s and one accumulation, and a 600 1/mm grating. Data acquisition was performed using LabSpec software (v. 6.8.1.9), while particle identification was carried out with IDFinder software (v. 4.2, HORIBA France SAS). Each detected particle was then classified as a specific polymer type by comparison with an internal spectral library containing reference spectra of the most common plastic polymers. Spectra with a Hit Quality Index (HQI) > 80 % were automatically assigned to PET while those with 60 % < HQI < 80 % were manually verified.

μ-RAMAN (Parma)

Analysis was performed on milk samples using a Horiba LabRAM HR Evolution μRaman spectrometer (Horiba, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a liquid-nitrogen CCD detector. Daily calibration was performed using the characteristic silicon Raman band at 520.7 cm^{-1} .

An overview of the entire filter was obtained using a 10x objective (Olympus MPlan N 10x/0.25) under brightfield mode. Based on this overview, two non-overlapping regions (2.5 mm x 2 mm each, 5 mm^2) were analyzed using a 50x objective (Olympus LMPlanFL N 50x/0.50), covering approximately 50 % of the total filtration area.

Spectral analysis was performed using the LabSpec6 (LS6) software. Particle counting, size measurement, morphological analysis, and spectral evaluation were carried out using the LS6 ParticleFinder™ application. Compound identification was achieved by comparing the acquired spectra with both Horiba reference libraries and a custom-made spectral library.

User-defined morphological thresholds were applied to minimise noise and distinguish particles from the background using a real-time video image.

Spectra were collected in the 415–2060 cm^{-1} range using a 532 nm excitation laser (25 mW power on the sample), with an acquisition time of 1 s and collecting two accumulations in order to remove spikes. A 600 lines/mm grating was used. The spectra were normalized and subjected to a polynomial baseline correction.

Spectra with a Hit Quality Index (HQI) > 80 % were automatically assigned to PET. Spectra with HQI values between 50 % and 80 % were manually reviewed to confirm the identification.

QCL-LDIR (UDC)

The measurements were performed using an 8700 tuneable quantum-cascade laser-based chemical imaging LDIR system, from Agilent Technologies, in the mid-IR region ($1800\text{-}975\text{ cm}^{-1}$), with its associated software: Clarity (v. 1.7.17). The particles were deposited over gold-coated filters (i3 Membranes GmbH). The instrumental conditions were the usual ones: "Particle analysis" working mode, wavenumber for the compilation of the preliminary IR image: 1442 cm^{-1} , particle size working range: $20\text{-}5000\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, sensitivity: 8, autoscan (no image collection), scan speed: fast, sweep speed: fast.

5 Results

5.1 Basic characterization of matrices

Infant milk powder

The infant milk powder or often also called baby milk was purchased from a local supermarket in Berlin, Germany. (HiPP PRE BIO COMBIOTIK for newborns). A similar infant milk powder, from the same brand and with the same elemental composition, was purchased from a local supermarket in A Coruña, Spain, Turin and Parma, Italy.

An overview about the results of basic characterisation is given in table 3.

Table 3: Basis characterisation of milk powder

Analysis Method	Parameter	Unit	Sample	Partner
TGA	Organic content	%	98.3	UBA
	Inorganic Residue	%	1.7	
TOC		mg/g	508	UBA
ICP-OES	Na	mg/g	0.91	UBA
	Ca	mg/g	3.94	
	Mg	mg/g	0.35	
	Fe	mg/g	0.10	
	Zn	mg/g	0.03	
	Cu	µg/g	3.70	
	Mn	µg/g	0.02	

Suspended particulate matter

Suspended particulate matter (SPM) sample material was collected between 25.07.2023 and 29.08.2023 from the Elbe River near Geesthacht, Germany. The SPM material was collected using a sedimentation box simulating the natural sedimentation process in a natural river system. The sampling was conducted over a period of 36 days corresponding to a water volume of 328,204 m³, which has been pumped through the system. Harvested material was homogenized in a defined volume of the original river water and the entire volume (ca. 20 L) was frozen at -80 °C and subsequently freeze dried for about 6 weeks using a Christ Freeze Dryer. The dried material was transferred to a precleaned brown glass bottle, and the fine powder was homogenized for two days on a tilt/roller mixer. The material was not further homogenized by milling to maintain the natural particle size distribution of the SPM material. 10 aliquots of around 50 g were taken from the bulk sample into 100 mL glass bottles (additionally sealed with an aluminium cap) and shipped to the project partners. All glass sample vessels were prepared by rinsing them with Type I reagent-grade water (>18.2 MΩ cm) and ethanol, followed by a final heat treatment at 200 °C for 12 h. The aliquots should be stored in a dark, dry environment to avoid impacts of moisture.

An overview about the results of basic characterisation is given in Table 4

Table 4: Basis characterisation of SPM (n = number of measurements, HQ= Hit Quality)

Analysis Method	Parameter	Unit	Sample	Partner
TGA	Organic content	%	35.2	UBA
	Inorganic Residue	%	64.8	
TOC		mg/g	53.6	UBA
Loss on Ignition	Organic Content	%	34.8 ± 0.1	HEREON
	Inorganic Content	%	65.2 ± 0.1	
Particle Size	< 63 µm	%	84.7 ± 1.5	HEREON
SMP Background (QCL-LDIR)	Sum of PE, PET, PP	n (20 - 100 µm)	21 (HQ > 0.9)	HEREON
			107 (HQ > 0.7)	
SMP Background (ATR-FTIR)	Sum of PE, PET, PP, PMMA, PU, PS, PVC, EVA	n (< 50 - 100 µm)	45	IHi
		n (100 - 1000 µm)	40	
SMP Background (Py-GC-MS)	PET (n=10)	µg/g	36.6 ± 6.55	UDC
	PE (n=10)	µg/g	1,559 ± 175	
	PS (n=10)	µg/g	22.3 ± 4.23	
ICP-MS/MS	Ca	mg/g	20 ± 0.1	HEREON
	Mg	mg/g	3.96 ± 0.3	
	Fe	mg/g	15.9 ± 0.7	
	Zn	mg/g	0.46 ± 0.04	
	Cu	µg/g	382 ± 17	
	Mn	µg/g	1,130 ± 60	

5.2 Infant milk powder using mass determination methods

For milk powder sample pre-treatment using water and hydrogen peroxide treatments were performed. However, related to the subsequent detection these protocols were not meaningful, because of interferences in the SPM specific signals were found.

A meaningful solution was the application of citric acid. For this various concentrations and treatment conditions were optimized. It was found that an optimum was achieved, when 10 g of infant baby milk powder was mixed with 35 mL of 1% citric acid solution and stirred using a magnetic glass stirring rod at 50 °C for 90 minutes. This procedure removes more than 99% of the matrix.

For the spiking experiment (**sample preparation method Milk-1**) with SMP and subsequent **TED-GC/MS** and **Py-GC/MS** measurements, 5 g of milk powder was weighed in a glass bottle (250 ml) and 100 mL of MilliQ water (room temperature or 50 °C) was added. One tablet of PET (~ 20 µg) was added. The closed bottle was shaken by hand for 30 seconds and placed in an ultrasonic bath for 5 minutes. After that, 1 g of citric acid was added to the solution and shaken by hand for 30 seconds. The closed glass bottle was then placed in an ultrasonicated for 5 minutes. The milk solution was shaken for 10 seconds by hand and poured into the funnel of the filtration system and filtered. The filtration funnel and the filter were rinsed with abundant MilliQ water and the system was checked for possible leakages before filtration of the sample. To collect all the residue from the glass bottle, this was rinsed 3 times with 50 mL of MilliQ water (50 °C) and another time with 50 mL Ethanol. The funnel was then again rinsed with 50 mL MilliQ water and 50 mL Ethanol using a glass pipette. After the complete filtration of the sample and the rinsing process, the filter was carefully placed in a glass petri dish and dried at 50 °C for at least 2-4 hours.

For TED-GC/MS measurements, the milk was filtered through a filtration system under a fume hood and the residue was collected on a stainless-steel filter crucible 6 µm pore size, 13 mm diameter. For Py-GC/MS a glass microfiber filter (55 mm, 0.7 µm pore size) was weighted on an analytical balance. Triplicates were performed.

The results of this protocol are listed in table 5.

Table 5: Results of SMP in spiked milk powder using mass determination methods
(* Reference value according to homogeneity control with TGA)

		Sample preparation method (number of repetitions)	Composition of sample		Result		
			Matrix	SMP in tablet*	SMP mass	Recovery rate	LOD (LOQ)
			g	µg / tablet	µg / g milk	%	µg
TED-GC/MS	BAM	Milk-1 n=3	5	19.6 ± 1.8 (PET batch 2)	18.6 ± 3.1	95 ± 16	0.22 (0.44)
Py-GC/MS	UDC	Milk-1 n=3	5	19.6 ± 1.8 (PET batch 2)	19.0 ± 2.5	97 ± 13	0.15 (0.28)

- SOP “Sample preparation for the determination of microplastics in milk powder by use of citric acid and higher temperature” (available on Zenodo)

A publication “A fast and new sample preparation of milk powder for the analysis of microplastics using thermothermo-analytical nalaytic methodes” by Yosri Wiesner, Claudia Drago, Verónica Fernández-González, Carmen Moscoso-Pérez, Ulrike Braun, Soledad Muniategui Lorenzo, Korinna Altmann is in preparation and will be submitted soon.

5.3 Infant milk powder using particle determination methods

For the optimization of sample pretreatment of milk powder matrix with subsequent determination of particles using μ -FTIR or μ -Raman (**sample preparation method Milk-2**) an existing digestion protocol was used with slight modifications to improve the removal of organic material while preserving the integrity of chemically sensitive polymers, such as PET, enabling the development of a new method for reliable SMPs detection in complex matrices.

Powder milk was reconstituted with ultrapure water (14 % w/v) and shaken at 40 °C for 15 min in a shaking water bath (Ultrasonic Cleaner DU-45, 180 W). Meanwhile, a PET tablet was dissolved in 20 mL of ultrapure water in a glass flask. After the complete dissolution of the tablet, 25 mL of reconstituted milk was added to the solution, which was then heated to 40 °C while stirring to perform the digestion process. The milk sample was subjected to a multi-enzymatic digestion by adding and stirring 2 mL of multi-enzymatic detergent (Prozyme) for 2 min, followed by the addition of 10 mL of calcium chelating agent sodium ethylene diamine tetra acetate (EDTA-Na 0.5M, pH 8) for 3 min. Subsequently, 2 mL of alkaline solution tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH 25% v/v) were added under continuous stirring and the temperature was raised to 80 °C to initiate hot alkaline hydrolysis.

Upon reaching 80 °C, the hot digested milk was immediately transferred to a filtration unit (100 mL funnel, glass holder with 13 mm frit) and filtered under vacuum (N816 LABOPORT/100W) using a circular silicon filter with a pore size of 5 μ m (macroporus silicon membrane, 9 mm diameter, SmartMembrane) with an effective circular filtration area of approximately 20 mm² (~ 5 mm diameter).

Before filtration, the funnel was conditioned by rinsing with 15 mL of Triton™ X-100 (0.1 % v/v in ultrapure water) and 15 mL of ethanol (99.9 % v/v). The glass flask containing the digested milk was also rinsed with 15 mL of Triton™ X-100 (0.1 % v/v in ultrapure water) and 15 mL of ethanol (99.9 % v/v) to recover any MP PET particles adhering to its surfaces. The retained digested material on the Si filter was flushed sequentially with 5 mL of ultrapure water, 5 mL of nitric acid (5 % v/v in ultrapure water) and 10 mL of ultrapure water.

Finally, the funnel was rinsed again with 15 mL respectively of Triton™ X-100 (0.1 % v/v in ultrapure water) and 15 mL of ethanol (99.9 % v/v) to recover any particles potentially adhering to its surfaces. The filter was then stored in closed glass petri dishes until analysis. Following the same procedure, procedural blanks were performed using ultrapure water to evaluate any potential MP contamination introduced during the digestion procedure.

For the application of **QCL-LDIR** measurements (**sample preparation method Milk-3**) 1 g of milk powder was dissolved in a glass beaker with 125 mL of pre-filtered Milli-Q water. Heat at 40 °C. Filter the resulting milk solution (at 40 °C) through a stainless-steel filter (10 μ m mesh). Transfer the filter to a 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask. Wash the glass funnel and the O-ring with 2 % SDS. A subsequent digestion is done in two steps: (1) Add 100 mL of a 2 % (w/v) SDS solution and incubate for 24 h at 40° C and 130 U/min. (2) Add 100 mL of 30 % hydrogen peroxide gradually (5 mL steps and wait for foam diminution). Incubate for 48 h at 40 °C and 130 U/min.

Filtrate through a stainless-steel filter and wash the flask with 0.1 % Triton X-100 (or 2 % SDS) and pour over the filtration system. Rinse with abundant water (ca. 2 L). Then, transfer the contents of the stainless-steel filter to gold-coated ones. For this, submerge the stainless-steel filter in a 50 % water:ethanol mixture. Sonicate for 10 min at 32 Hz and, then, 10 min at 90 Hz. Remove the filter and wash it carefully with a 50 % water:ethanol mixture into a round-bottom tube. Filter the suspension through the gold filter, avoiding clogging. Transfer to a Petri dish and dry at 40 °C.

The results of these protocols are listed in table 6.

Table 6: Results of SMP in spiked milk powder using particle determination methods
 (*Target values according to measurement of the neat tablet with the corresponding methods)

		Sample preparation method (number of repetitions)	Composition of sample		Results	
			Matrix	SMP in tablet*	Particle numbers	Recovery rate
			g	N /tablet	N / mg	%
μ -FTIR	INRIM	Milk-2 (n=6)	14	751 \pm 194 PET (batch 2)	762 \pm 26	102 \pm 27
				60 \pm 14 PET (batch 3)	48 \pm 11	80 \pm 26
μ -RAMAN	INRiM	Milk-2 (n=6)	14	1759 \pm 141 PET (batch 2)	1448 \pm 253	82 \pm 16
				160 \pm 22 PET (batch 3)	131 \pm 16	82 \pm 15
μ -RAMAN	Parma	Milk-2 (n=6)	14	1759 \pm 141 PET (batch 2)	1500 \pm 204	85 \pm 14
				160 \pm 22 PET (batch 3)	140 \pm 24	88 \pm 19
QCL-LDIR	UDC	Milk-3 (n=1)	1	609 \pm 232 PET (batch 2)	424	70

- SOP "Sample preparation for identification and quantification of small microplastics in infant milk formula by vibrational spectroscopy" (soon available on Zenodo)

A publication "Validating Micro-Raman Spectroscopy Method for Small Microplastics (5-100 μ m) in Infant Milk Formula: An Inter-Laboratory Study with Reference Materials" by Mara Putzu, Marta Barbaresi, Marta Fadda, Alessio Sacco, Maurizio Piergiovanni, Matteo Masino, Federica Bianchi, Korinna Altmann, Nizar Benismail, Laureen Coïc, Ivana Fenoglio, Monica Mattarozzi, Andrea Mario Rossi, Maria Careri and Andrea Mario Giovannozzi" submitted to Talanta Open TALO-D-25-00359, 16.09.2025.

5.4 SPM using mass determination methods

For SPM sample pretreatments using **TED-GC/MS** to workflows were investigated. In the first, SPM and SMP were only resuspended in water and then filtrated. The filter was then analyzed, without any further treatment. In the second workflow, a higher SPM content was taken, and an additional density separation step was performed.

In the first protocol (**sample preparation method SPM-1.1**) 20 mg of SPM together with one tablet of PP was resolved (incl. ultrasonic treatment) in 1 L of MilliQ water. Solids of sample were filtrated using vacuum filtration on a stainless-steel filter crucible 6 μm pore size, 13 mm diameter, which were than analyzed by TED-/GC/MS.

In the second protocol (**sample preparation method SPM-1.2**) 500 mg of SPM was resolved (incl. ultrasonic treatment) in 30 mL of MilliQ water together with one tablet of PP. This solution was given to CaCl_2 solution and transferred in shaking funnel ($V=1$ L). The sedimentation took place over night, a residual volume 50 mL was taken for filtration on a stainless-steel filter crucible 6 μm pore size, 13 mm diameter, which were than analyzed by TED-/GC/MS. Triplicates were performed.

In the third protocol, using **Py-GC/MS (sample preparation method SPM-2)** 10 mg of SPM was resolved in 30 mL of MilliQ water together with one tablet of PET (Batch 2). This solution was filtrated using a stainless-steel filter holder with a Whatman glass fibre filter (13 mm filter size, 1.6 μm pore size) and a 20 mL glass syringe connected to a VisiprepTM vacuum manifold (Supelco Sigma-Aldrich Co). The filter was folded and inserted into the pyrolysis ECO-cup (80 μl , Frontier Labs) and dried in an oven at 40°C for a minimum of 4 hours, then samples were placed directly into the pyrolyzer. 20 μl of TMAH (25% in MeOH) as derivatizing agent was added to the cup since, the pyrolysis marker for PET, benzoic acid is influenced by the sample matrix, SPM, and therefore cannot be used. After derivatization, the marker used for PET quantification becomes dimethyl terephthalate (m/z 163, 194, 135).

The results of this protocol are listed in table 7.

Table 7: Results of SMP in spiked SPM powder using mass determination methods (* Reference value according to homogeneity control with TGA)

		Sample preparation method (number of repetitions)	Composition of sample		Result	
			Matrix	SMP tablets	SMP mass/sample	Recovery rate
			mg	μg / tablet	μg / sample	%
TED-GC/MS	BAM	SPM-1.1 (n=3)	20 mg	19.3 \pm 3.7 μg PP (batch 2)	19.6 \pm 2.6	131 \pm 17
TED-GC/MS	BAM	SPM-1.2 (n=3)	500 mg	19.3 \pm 3.7 μg PP (batch 2)	18.9 \pm 2.2	125 \pm 15
Py-GC/MS	UDC	SPM-2 (n=5)	10 mg	19.6 \pm 1.8 μg PET (batch 2)	18.3 \pm 2.5	107 \pm 14

5.5 SPM using particle determination methods

For SPM various combinations and workflows of hydrogen peroxide in various concentrations, including SDS and density separation treatments were performed. A final optimized protocol with satisfactory recovery rate could not be determined for the targeted spiking level.

For μ -FTIR measurement 2.6 - 2.8 mg of SPM, together with 1 tablet of PET were treated with 50 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 %) at 40 °C for 24h. The sample was then filtrated using an anodisk filter with pore size of 0,2 μ m (diameter 25 mm) (**sample preparation method SPM-3.1**)

Alternatively, 50 and 100 mg of SPM was chosen, together with 1 tablet of PET. First, a density separation using NaI for 48h was applied. The sample was then filtrated through stainless steel filter (10 μ m) and filtration residue was then treated with 50 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 %) at 40 °C for 24h. The sample was then filtrated using an anodisk filter with pore size of 0.2 μ m (diameter 25 mm) (**sample preparation method SPM-3.2**)

A third workflow was to start with two subsequent density separation steps using NaI for 48h, filtration on stainless steel filters (10 μ m), then treatment with 50 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 %) at 40 °C for 24h. The sample was then filtrated using an anodisk filter with pore size of 0.2 μ m (diameter 25 mm) (**sample preparation method SPM-3.3**).

The sample preparation was performed also in reverse order so that first 50 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 %) at 40 °C for 24h, then filtration with stainless steel filter (10 μ m) and finally density separation with NaI for 24h was applied. The sample was then filtrated using an anodisk filter with pore size of 0.2 μ m (diameter 25 mm) (**sample preparation method SPM-3.4**).

Finally, for shortening the preparation time. the treatment of first density separation with NaI for only 24 h, Filtration on stainless steel filters (10 μ m) and then 50 mL of hydrogen peroxide (30 %) at 40 °C for 24h was performed. The sample was then filtrated using an anodisk filter with pore size of 0.2 μ m (diameter 25 mm) (**sample preparation method SPM-3.5**).

Further investigations by PlasticTrace partners, using different filters do not result in meaningful results and are therefore are not protocolled here.

For **QCL-LDIR** measurements at UDC two sample treatment procedures were followed: Oxidative digestions and density separation plus centrifugation. For digestion using H₂O₂ (**sample preparation method SPM-4.1**), SPM sample aliquots between 3 and 5 mg are dissolved in 100 mL of a 2 % SDS solution and incubated for 48 h (40 °C, 130 U/min), then 100 mL of H₂O₂ are added and incubated again for 48 h. The suspension was then filtered through stainless-steel filters (47 mm diameter, 10 μ m mesh size). The filter cake was resuspended in bottom-rounded glass tubes in 30-40 mL of an 1:1 Ethanol : H₂O mixture and sonication (5 min at 32 Hz and 5 min at 80 Hz). The resulting suspension is then filtered through gold-coated filters (it is suggested to use two gold-coated filters sequentially to avoid clogging).

In the second protocol, density separation with CaCl₂ plus centrifugation was performed (**sample preparation method SPM-4.2**). SPM sample aliquots between 25 and 100 mg are introduced in 50 mL centrifuge tubes, 30 mL of saturated CaCl₂ solution added and –optionally- spike with a standard tablet containing microplastics (as obtained in the PlasticTrace project, either from “Batch 2” (for 25 and 100 mg SPM aliquots) or “Batch 3” (for 50 and 100 mg SPM aliquots)).

Before centrifuging the tubes (20 min at 3000 rpm) agitate them vigorously (Vortex at 1400 rpm, 15 min). The resulting suspensions were rest for some minutes and decant the supernatant into corresponding clean glass beakers. The beakers were covered with aluminum foil and keep for subsequent steps.

The procedure was repeated three additional times. For this, around 20 mL of fresh saturated CaCl₂ solution was added to the centrifuge tubes, agitate, centrifuge and decant as previously. The three new extracts for each tube were poured into the same beakers as the first ones. Mildly heat the overall extract of the beaker to 40-50 °C until no CaCl₂ crystals were seen anymore. Then, start filtering under vacuum, through gold-coated filters (avoiding clogging) was done.

The beakers and funnels were carefully rinsed with a 50:50 Ethanol : H₂O solution to the filtration device. The filters in Petri dishes were placed and dry in an oven at 40 °C.

The results obtained using these protocols are listed in Table 8.

*Table 8: Results of SMP in spiked SMP using particle determination methods
(*Target values according to measurement of the neat tablet with the corresponding methods)*

		Sample preparation method (number of repetitions)	Composition of sample		Results	
			Matrix	SMP in tablet*	Particle numbers/ sample	Recovery rate
			mg	number	N/ mg SPM	%
μ-FTIR	Syke	SPM-3.1 (n = 3)	2,7	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	261 ± 21	92.4 ± 3.8
		SPM-3.2 (n = 1)	50	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	5	36
			100	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	3	35
		SPM-3.3 (n = 1)	50	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	5	31
			100	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	2	21
		SPM-3.4 (n = 1)	50	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	2	15
			100	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	0	3
		SPM-3.5 (n = 1)	50	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	3	22
			100	751 ± 208 PET (batch 2)	1	8
		QCL-LDIR	UDC	SPM-4.1 (n = 2)	5	609 ± 232 PET (batch 2)
SPM-4.2 (n = 2)	25			609 ± 232 PET (batch 2)	14 ± 8	57 ± 35
	100			609 ± 232 PET (batch 2)	4 ± 2	72 ± 36
SPM-4.2 (n = 1)	50			72 ± 8 PET (batch 3)	0.7	47
SPM-4.2 (n = 3)	100			72 ± 8 PET (batch 3)	0.4	57 ± 12

SOP "Sample preparation for the determination of microplastics in suspended particulate matter (SPM) from surface water, considering different target values" (soon available on Zenodo)

6 Conclusions

In sum two finalized SOPs for the spiking of milk with PET were provided. This matrix only needs a reduction of organic matrix. Acceptable recovery rates of more than 80 % with error derivations of around 10 - 20 % were determined for mass determination and particle number-based methods. However, the assumed target value for a proposed realistic SMP contamination in milk, < 10 n/g or < 0.01 µg/g (Table 1), is not covered by the protocols using thermo-analytic methods (~ 4 µg/g), but nearly by the protocols using spectroscopic methods (~10-100 n/g).

For SPM with PET or PP only indicative information could be implemented in the SOP. This matrix needs a reduction of organic and inorganic matrix and is therefore more complex. However, recovery rates of more around 120 % with error derivations of around 10 - 20 % were determined for mass determination. For detection methods of particle number-based methods only good recovery rates were determined for very high spiking levels. For moderate and realistic spiking levels only recovery rates of less than 50 % could be developed. Here the number of repetitions is still very low. The assumed target value for a proposed realistic SMP contamination > 20,000 n/g or > 20 µg/g (Table 1) is covered by the protocols using thermo-analytic methods (~ 40 - 2,000 µg/g), and by the protocols using spectroscopic methods (~8,000 - 280,000 n/g; 6,000 - 200,000 n/g; 700 - 1,500 n/g).

During the development of all SOPs, it became very clear that protocols developed with thermo-analytical SMP detection are faster to realize than with spectroscopic methods. However, with thermo-analytical methods only relatively high levels can be reliably analyzed here compared to the matrix. The application of spectroscopic methods is therefore preferred, when low SMP contamination are expected in a matrix.